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Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

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Distribution of soil biodiversity groups across Europe

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1. Introduction

Soils harbor a large portion of global biodiversity, including microorganisms (e.g., bacteria), micro- (e.g., Nematoda), meso- (e.g., Collembola), and macrofauna (e.g., Oligochaeta). This high biodiversity plays critical roles driving multiple ecosystem functions and services, including climate regulation, nutrient cycling, and food production. Recent studies showed that local scale variations in soil biodiversity is of high importance for the maintenance of multifunctionality (i.e. the ability of ecosystems to simultaneously provide multiple ecosystem functions and services) in terrestrial ecosystems. Nevertheless, and with few exceptions (Orgiazzi et al., 2016), soil biodiversity data were not collected in a harmonized and standardized manner across European agroecosystems.

The main aim of this study is to collect European soil biodiversity data in a standardized template, harmonize data and associated metadata to provide an overview of existing data on different biological groups.

2. Methodological approach

Data sources and reports were identified through a web search and literature review using a combination of key terms (e.g. biodiversity, conservation, data, data set, database). To implement the biological measurements collection, we gathered a group of experts on soil biodiversity. Several rounds of workshops were carried out and five templates were defined to collect the most exhaustively possible soil biodiversity indicators (macrofauna, Mesofauna, microfauna, bacteria and fungi). Templates were standardized to have uniform terminologies on site characteristics, agricultural management practices, sampling method, methods used for analyses, soil characteristics, soil biological indicators, soil taxa, and indices.

Study description

Detailed and standardized templates were developed

Field order	Name	Management description		Soil description																																																														
1	<u>ID_Field</u>	Field order	Name	Field order	Name	Definition																																																												
2	<u>ID_Subsample</u>						3	Observation_level	6	<u>Longitude</u>	4	<u>Date_subsample_collection</u>	3	Observation_level	If reported data are referred to : the sample the subsample	7	<u>Latitude</u>	8	Altitude	10	Study_Landuse	5	Farming_system	4	<u>Date_subsample_collection</u>	Date of organism /biological sampling. Standard format is according to ISO 8601: YYYY-MM-DD. Any level of precision (year (Y), month (M) or day (D)) is possible.	11	Experimental_type	5	Soil_type_WRB	The soil type according to the World Reference Base for soil resources (WRB).	12	Total_Experiment_duration	6	WRB_version	Date of WRB version	13	Experiment_duration_mean	7	Soil_taxonomy_version	If you used the soil taxonomy to name the soil, indicate the date of the version you used.	14	Date_start_experiment	8	Soil_type_in_soil_taxonomy	The soil type according to the soil taxonomy	15	Date_end_experiment	9	Name_local_soil_classification	If you name the soil according to a local soil classification, indicate the name of this classification			10	Soil_type_in_a_local_classification	The soil type according to the local classification			11	PH_method	Methodology to assess the pH : KCl CaCl2 Water			12	pH_mean	Mean of pH between samples
3	Observation_level						6	<u>Longitude</u>	4	<u>Date_subsample_collection</u>						3	Observation_level	If reported data are referred to : the sample the subsample	7	<u>Latitude</u>	8			Altitude	10	Study_Landuse	5	Farming_system	4	<u>Date_subsample_collection</u>	Date of organism /biological sampling. Standard format is according to ISO 8601: YYYY-MM-DD. Any level of precision (year (Y), month (M) or day (D)) is possible.	11	Experimental_type	5	Soil_type_WRB	The soil type according to the World Reference Base for soil resources (WRB).	12	Total_Experiment_duration	6	WRB_version	Date of WRB version	13	Experiment_duration_mean	7	Soil_taxonomy_version	If you used the soil taxonomy to name the soil, indicate the date of the version you used.	14	Date_start_experiment	8	Soil_type_in_soil_taxonomy	The soil type according to the soil taxonomy	15	Date_end_experiment	9	Name_local_soil_classification	If you name the soil according to a local soil classification, indicate the name of this classification			10	Soil_type_in_a_local_classification	The soil type according to the local classification			11	PH_method	Methodology to assess the pH : KCl CaCl2 Water
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Method Bacteria description Detailed and standardized templates were developed for all five biological groups

Field order	Name	Definition
1	<u>ID_Field</u>	Identification of the plot. The format is Country code(2 alpha-code ISO3166)_Site name_ number of the field.
2	<u>ID_Subsample</u>	Identification of the subsample. Depending on the sample design, subsample may refer to a biological replicate; biological replicates are generally obtained by combining 3-6 subsample replicates (following for example the LUCAS sampling scheme). The format is Country code(2 alpha-code ISO3166)_Site name_ number of the field_ field methodology_ number subsample.
3	Observation_Level	If reported data are referred to : the sample the subsample
4	<u>Date_Subsample_Collection</u>	Date of organism /biological sampling. Standard format is according to ISO 8601: YYYY-MM-DD. Any level of precision (year (Y), month (M) or day (D)) is possible.
6	Bacteria_Soil_Subsample_Mass	Mass of each subsample for bacteria DNA extract
7	Bacteria_Sampling_Methodology	Indicate the methodology to collect soil sample Soil_core Spade
8	Bacteria_Sampling_Methodology_ISO	Indicate if possible the ISO for the used sampling methodology
9	Bacterial_Methodology_Class	Please indicate if a sequencing or a fingerprinting (T-RFLP, DGGE) methodology was used: Sequencing T-RFLP DGGE PLFA Other

Field order	Name	Definition
1	<u>ID_Field</u>	Identification of the plot. The format is Country code(2 alpha-code ISO3166)_Site name_ number of the field.
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3	<u>Observation_level</u>	If reported data are referred to : the sample the subsample
4	<u>Date_subsample_collection</u>	Date of organism /biological sampling. Standard format is according to ISO 8601: YYYY-MM-DD. Any level of precision (year (Y), month (M) or day (D)) is possible.
5	Bacteria_Fisher_Alpha	Bacteria Fisher Alpha
6	Bacteria_Richness_Index	Richness index for bacteria community
7	Bacteria_Chao1_Index	Chao1 Index of bacteria community
8	Bacteria_Shannon_Index	Shannon Index for bacteria
9	Bacteria_Shannon_Index_logbase	Indicate the logarithm base used for Shannon index calculation
10	Bacteria_Simpson_Index	Simpson Index for bacteria community
11	Bacteria_Ace_Index	Ace index for bacteria community
12	Bacteria_Inverse_Simpson_Index	Inverse Simpson Index community
13	Bacteria_Evenness_Index	Evenness index of bacteria community
14	Bacteria_Evenness_Index_method	Indicate the method used for Evenness index calculation (for example Pielou's)
15	Bacteria_Phylogenetic_Diversity	Phylogenetic diversity of bacteria community
16	Acidisoma_Relative_Abundance	Indicate the relative abundance of Acidisoma genus from 0 to 1

Example of template sheets covering various sections of metadata and observed data

Once templates were finalized data collection from inventory of data sources (D2.1) was initiated through 5 dedicated tasks on dedicated soil biological groups (macrofauna, Mesofauna, microfauna, bacteria and fungi).

We used three methods to collect information on existing datasets: based on publications, open repositories, personal contact.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Macrofauna

The Macrofauna dataset contains almost 9,000 samples, spread over 35 European countries. The majority of datapoints are in Germany (19.5%), Great Britain (14.9%), Italy (9.3%), France (8.2%), the Netherlands (7.6%), Austria (7.6%) and Poland (5.8%). Specific geographical distribution of points can be seen in Figure 1. However, note that this does not include around 20% of data points which do not have corresponding geographical coordinates.

Figure 1 Distribution of WP2 data points in Europe.

Of those data points 47.6% are grassland, 37.4% are arable land, 5.4% are vineyards and orchards. While 22 different soil types are included in the dataset, the most common ones are Cambisol (27.7%), Histosol (11.8%), Luvisol (7.9%) and Leptosol (5.5%).

Agricultural metadata is sometimes only sporadically available. However, in most cases at least the land use, crop, crop type, and farming system are known (information available for more than 70% of data points). As for soil metadata, this information is even more sporadic, with only WRB soil type being consistently available (74.8% of data points). Other parameters such as soil texture and pH-value are available for around 30% of data points.

As for earthworm data, the dataset contains a total abundance of more than 1.8 million earthworms, with a mean abundance of 147 individuals per m². Half of the earthworms were identified to genus level or higher, with around a third of the earthworms belonging to the species *Aporrectodea caliginosa* (31.5%). Apart from that, *Allolobophora chlorotica* (15.3%), *Aporrectodea rosea* (11.2%), and *Lumbricus rubellus* (6.2%) are the most abundant species overall. In total, 117 different earthworm species can be found in the data collection, not including subspecies.

When splitting the earthworm abundance into ecological groups according to the different species, endogeic earthworm species were most abundant (68.3%), followed by epigeic (13.0%), epi-aneic (6.1%), and anecic ones (3.6%). In addition, 9.0% of earthworm abundance could not be assigned to ecological groups (Figure 2).

Figure 1 Distribution of earthworm abundances in dataset into ecological groups.

3.2 Mesofauna

Overview of mesofauna data

Lorenzo D'Avino CREA, Italy Elena Tondini CREA, Italy Giovanni L'Abate CREA, Italy

Data providers	Project	n° sampling sites
CNR	ANR_SOILWARM	1
CREA-AA	EXALIBUR	17
CREA-DC	MONACO	3
Lorenzo D'Avino		2
ERSAF	ACQUA&SOLE	4
ERSAF	QBS PRATI	60
ERSAF	SOIL4LIFE	16
ARPA Friuli Venezia Giulia	REG. MONITORING	20
INRAE	OFB_DYNABIO	10
INRAE	ANR_SOILWARM	1
BOKU	VINEDIVERS	16

QBS-ar, QBS-ar BF, abundance of Enchytraeids species, Collembola species, presence/absence, or abundance of biological forms (BF) of mesofauna (microarthropods).

Overall, data from nine projects were collected. The majority of sites are situated in the Mediterranean Mountains (43%), followed by the Mediterranean North (31%), Atlantic Central (11%), and Pannonian (8%) regions. Only a few sites are located in the Continental, Lusitanian, and Mediterranean South environmental zones.

CNR provides microarthropods biological forms data from an integrated pest management vineyard fertilized with different amount of Biochar.

The Excalibur project aims to evaluate organic and conventional farming management in various annual and perennial crops such as tomatoes, strawberries, and apple orchards. It provides data on microarthropods biological forms. Sampling sites are located in Italy, Poland, Austria, Denmark, and Germany.

Monaco project regards microarthropods biological forms data on trials to monitor effect of European policy measures, in 3 sites in Italy sampled in two different times.

Summary of biodiversity data collected for task 2.2.4 : Data and metadata related to Fungi

Erica Lumini CNR, Italy ; Francesco Vitali CREA, Italy

An overall assessment of alpha and beta diversity of **Fungi** communities in the collected samples is reported

Perspective:

- Fungal ecological guild data might be included in the database as a description of each Fungi genera. Data in the MINOTAUR database record the relative abundance of a selection of soil Fungi genera (see below) in the different samples. A separated section of the database might be created in the future to record ecological guild (i.e. a method for classification of Fungi on the basis of functional traits) for all of those genera.

Overcome problems related to PacBio Fungal sequences in LUCAS (using ITS1 as target region)

1) Firstly, identification of the measurable and traceable characteristics, considered important for the initial definition of a list of parameters relating to the biodiversity of Fungi, Bacteria & Archaea, was prepared based on previous and current projects and literature data. This initial selection served as base for design of the sheets in the MINOTAUR template relevant to our task for defining, particularly, the variables to be collected and the metadata for their description.

2) As a result, in collaboration with T2.2.5 colleagues, we prepared a first version of the common template sheets for data collection for Fungi, Bacteria & Archaea. As the study of those three soil communities typically relies on Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) techniques several metadata (specifically, those related to technical aspects of sequencing) and data (e.g. alpha diversity indices) are common between the three communities.

3) One of the main uncertainties we faced was the enormous taxonomic diversity, typical of microbial communities in soil. We could not simply include all possible thousands of soil Bacteria or Fungi genera and needed a reproducible selection criterion by which to include them. To this purpose, we concluded that the most comprehensive and authoritative European resource to refer to was LUCAS initiative. We contacted Dr. Alberto Orgiazzi (JRC) to informally obtain some of the LUCAS' data on Fungi & Bacteria retrieved from the 310 cropland sites in LUCAS (out of 715 total LUCAS sites).

4) Communities from 310 cropland sites in LUCAS were used to retrieve a list of Genera (Fungi and Bacteria) commonly found in soils across Europe. We focused on two complementary aspects of a community: abundance and frequency. From one side, we obtained from LUCAS the 50 most abundant genera in the cropland soils (i.e. mean relative abundance across all 310 sites), on the other hand we obtained the 30 most frequent genera, regardless of abundance (i.e. the genera most frequently present across all 310 sites).

5) The union of the two lists constitutes the last group of variables included in the MINOTAUR template. We also highlighted possible biases related to the use of the ITS as a target region for all fungi because, despite their recognized importance for agro ecosystems, taxa belonging to the AMF (Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Fungi) were not included in this composite list of Fungal genera, (Rennes, 4-7/10/2023).

6) Additionally, we highlighted problems related to the definition of sample and subsamples in MINOTAUR Database sheets, which were also discussed and reported (Minotaur midterm meeting Rennes, 4-7/10/2023)

Only some data from previous European projects (ECOFINDER, PURE, DIVERFARMING, EXCALIBUR) are available to implement the database.

4. Data availability

Data collected are being published in different steps. Collated data are uploaded in Minotaur database which will be made public by the end of November 2024.

• Data already available (August 2024)

	# data	Nb countries
<u>Earthworms</u>	9 000	35
<u>Enchytraeids</u>	561	3
<u>Collembola</u>	1 242	9
<u>Others (e.g. chilopodes...)</u>	631	9
<u>Nematodes</u>	1100	9
<u>Bacteria</u>	Tbc	24
<u>Fungi</u>	398	24

Earthworm distribution

Earthworm data are presented in various conferences EGU2024, IUSS2024, ÖBG tagung2024. Mittmannsgruber, M., Peres, G., Murugan, R., and Zaller, J.: Earthworm populations and their drivers in agroecosystems across Europe: land use, soil properties, climatic factors, EGU General Assembly 2024, Vienna, Austria, 14–19 Apr 2024, EGU24-18198, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu24-18198>, 2024.

A publication on earthworm distribution and their drivers is under preparation.

Mesofauna distribution

D'Avino et al2024. Comparing soil fauna parameters and ecological indices to evaluate agronomic tillage and fertiliser management in European long-term experiments. EJPSOIL ASD2024

Predicting multitaxonomic diversity patterns

Overall conceptual drivers of soil biodiversity: drivers alter 5 biological groups differently and their interactions are vital to untangle complexity and their drivers (climate, management practices). This will include:

#Major drivers of 5 biological groups

#Interactions of biological groups and soil functions (together with T3.3 and T.3.2)
 #Time span of datasets analysed (eg. 1980-2020)? along with distribution of data in EU.
 #Time span of publication with positive and negative effects on soil biodiversity to explain how datasets evolved and got complex drivers assessed over time.

4. Conclusions

Large-scale international research projects usually include data management and sharing plans. However, smaller labs conducting more specialized studies, such as analyzing a single lake or tracking specific animal models, often lack such systems. As a result, their data tends to remain isolated within the lab and may be forgotten as team members move on.

For the scientific community, the lack of proper data management leads to wasted effort, missed collaboration opportunities, and issues with reproducibility.

FAIR (Findable Accessible, Interpretable and Reusable) data highlights that even less popular data can still be valuable and promotes best practices for data preservation and sharing, to safeguard data for the future. However, achieving this goal will require a unified effort and changes in lab culture. More than one-third of data identified (including fully open data and partially published on condition that data will be made available upon request) were not either accessible, lack metadata (published data), or essentially unusable.

These data sources were used for data collection in T2.2 and collected data were used in WP3 to assess the relationship between soil biological indicators and soil functions and to model (D5.1) macro and mesofauna distribution. The inventory will be made available at the end of the project together with the D2.2.

Lack of metadata makes data basically unusable. The problem of irreproducibility is compounded by the rise of big data, where large volumes of unformatted sources of data have been made accessible. However, lack of harmonized data, dataset metadata and standardized vocabularies were considered a primary stumbling block to reproducible research and decision-making using big data in national and international monitoring initiatives (eg. soil carbon farming, biodiversity monitoring, soil health etc.,). The data collected in this work provides an example of harmonized data that facilitates decision making, management assessments and modelling, which was carried out in Minotaur WP5 to map the distribution of selected biological indicators. (in D5.1 and D5.2).

Thus, it is essential to enhance the involvement of stakeholders in improving quality of data archiving and decision making.

5. References

- Tedersoo, L., Küngas, R., Oras, E. et al. Data sharing practices and data availability upon request differ across scientific disciplines. *Sci Data* 8, 192 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-021-00981-0>
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